

Minutes of the 50th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 24th January 2013
(This document was finalised on 28th March 2013)

Present:

Dr Helen Clark ²	(HAC)	
Mr Les Dean ^{1,4}	(LD)	
Mr David Edwards ³	(DE)	
Dr David Hooper ^{4,5}	(DAH)	Secretary
Dr Dirk Klugmann ³	(DK)	
Dr Chris Lee ⁷	(CFL)	
Dr Emily Norton ⁶	(EGN)	
Dr Jeremy Price ³	(JP)	
Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁶	(GV)	Chair

Affiliation:

¹Aberystwyth University

²Defence Science and Technology Laboratory

³Met Office

⁴NERC MST Radar Facility

⁵Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Manchester

⁷University of Reading

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BADC	British Atmospheric Data Centre
BL(WP)	Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
CLEARFLO	Clean Air For London (campaign)
COPE	COncvective Precipitation Experiment
DIAMET	DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms
DPW	Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FAAM	(NERC/Met Office) Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
FGAM	Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
I&Q	In-phase and Quadrature (radar samples)
IR	Infrared
JDE	Jon Eastment
JJ	Jon Jones (Met Office)
LCBR	Laser Cloud Base Recorder
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	(NERC) National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PC	Personal Computer
PCI	Peripheral Component Interconnect

PV	Potential Vorticity
RMS	Root Mean Square
S&F	(NERC) Services and Facilities
TROSIAD	TROpopause folding, Stratospheric Intrusions And Deep convection
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
USB	Universal Serial Bus
UT	Universal Time
VAA	Volcanic Ash Advisory (Met Office service)

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

DAH pointed out that he had mistakenly used action item number 48.4.1 twice on page 3 of the minutes of the 49th meeting. The second instance should have been numbered 48.4.2. This was despite the fact that he had spotted the same mistake in the minutes of the 48th meeting.

EGN had drawn DAH's attention to an error in section 5a of the minutes for the 47th meeting. DAH had given the magnetic declination at Cardington as -3° . It should have been approximately -1.7° at that time (July 2011) and was -1.45° on the day of the current meeting - see e.g. <http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag-web/>.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP, who was not the meeting, had reported to DAH that he was still following this up. However, Owen Cox, who had been the primary contact, has now left the Met Office. Consequently progress has been slow. DK reported, as an aside, that he (DK) had been unable to convince the Met Office's operations team to locate one of their new Mk 2 Nimbus ceilometers at the MST Radar site (one went to Aberporth instead). Nevertheless, he was hoping to bring a Mk 1 unit from Exeter after it has undergone a refurbishment. As yet, there is no definite time scale for this. The optics are the same on the two models, but the driver detector is closer to the breakthrough point on the Mk 2. Although this should make it more sensitive, it has perhaps makes it less robust.

ACTION ITEM 49.4.1 DAH to investigate, prior to carrying out action item 47.2.2, the cause for clearly-erroneous data points in the Met Office wind-profile messages being flagged as reliable.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made some progress on the second of these three items and that these were his highest priorities when he was not chasing hard deadlines.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

By contrast, this item is DAH's lowest priority.

ACTION ITEM 47.5.1 GAP to ensure that the BADC archive Met Office lightning data to cover the TROSIAD campaign period.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 48.4.2 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

ONGOING

This item will be dealt with in section 4g.

ACTION ITEM 49.3.1 DAH to provide GV with the integrated rainfall for the 8th - 9th June 2012 event.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that there had been an accumulation of 75.8 mm over the period 2012/06/07 00:00 - 2012/06/09 12:00 GMT. The bulk of this - 69.0 mm - fell quasi-continuously after 2012/06/07 23:00 GMT.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.1 GAP to create a link from the Cardington dataset webpage on the BADC to the FGAM wind-profiler page.

ONGOING

GAP had reported to DAH that he was currently preparing new FGAM web pages. In order to set up an appropriate archive structure, he requires further campaign details from EGN. JP reported, as an aside, that the Cardington web pages also needed updating.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.2 GAP to provide GV with access to images from the webcams that show sky conditions at the RAL site for the duration of the CLEARFLO campaign.

DISCONTINUED

GAP had reported to DAH that scaffolding around the buildings at RAL had obscured the view. Consequently he has unable to carry out this action.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units have indicated brief (~ 1 s) electricity supply disruptions on 10 occasions during the past six months: on 6th (twice), 24th, and 25th July 2012, on 25th August, on 12th September, on 1st and 4th November 2012, on 20th and 23rd (3 times) January 2013. There was a longer disruption (13 s) on 8th September 2012. None of these had any impact on the equipment powered by the UPS units.

3b) Telecommunications

A problem with a BADC computer, which started at around 17:00 UT on Friday 27th July 2012, prevented data from being uploaded from the MST Radar site until around 08:00 UT on the following Monday morning (30th). It took the rest of the Monday for the backlog of file transfers to clear. Another problem prevented files from being uploaded between approximately 22:00 UT on 22nd January 2013 and 08:00 the following morning.

There were 4 occasions when the broadband modem lost its internet connection: starting at 13:00 UT on Saturday 6th October 2012, at 17:52 UT on Sunday 16th December, at 00:51 UT on Wednesday 9th January 2013, and at 05:50 UT on Saturday 19th January 2013. In the first two cases the connection was not restored until the following Monday morning, when either LD or DPW had arrived on site and was able to power-cycle the modem. In the third and fourth cases, the connection was restored later the same day.

JP reported that the modem at Cardington was prone to the same problem, albeit more-frequently than four times in six months. He uses a timer switch to power-cycle the modem on a daily basis. This limits any outages to a maximum of 24 hours. DAH and LD reported that they were investigating a mobile phone based method of remotely power-cycling the modem.

ACTION ITEM 50.3.1 DAH and LD to implement a method of restoring lost broadband connections without anyone having to be at the radar site.

NEW

3c) Miscellaneous site issues

The relentlessly-wet weather of 2012 is thought to have been responsible for two problems at the site.

Firstly, the new wooden huts that house the MST radar primary power splitters within the antenna array are showing signs of water damage. They were constructed in March 2012 and their panels had been treated with wood stain. Nevertheless, the plywood layers are starting to separate in places at the bases of the panels. It seems likely that they have been soaking up rain water, which has been accumulating on the ground rather than draining away. Remedial work was undertaken during the autumn of 2012 in order to prevent further deterioration. This required the radar to be powered down for a few hours on 16th and 23rd October 2012. The base of each hut has been encircled with a wooden girdle and the load-bearing supports have been raised onto tiles. The aim of the latter is to minimise direct contact between the wood and the ground.

The second problem is that willow tree saplings have become established in the south-west corner of the MST radar antenna array. Willow is well-known for being both fast-growing and water-loving. The saplings appear to have grown by a metre in the space of a single season and some are in excess of two metres tall. They have proved resistant to weed spray, which is applied twice per year. The grass-cutter has inspected the area with a view to carrying out their removal. He suspects that the roots may have blocked the drains, which would have exacerbated the standing water problem. Moreover, he suspects that a reduction in rabbit activity has also contributed to this extra-ordinary growth. The rabbits would

normally keep the saplings in check.

For unrelated reasons, work is currently being undertaken to shore up the dilapidated wooden shed next to the lidar container. This was motivated by a visit to the site, on 19th October 2012, by NERC's asset evaluators. They pointed out that the shed was critical for operations owing to the fact that it houses the site's main electricity distribution board. Prior to this, it was regarded simply as a storage space. The shed is owned by Aberystwyth University, who last carried out maintenance on it when GV was still working for them. DAH could not see them continuing to take an interest in the structure and so the work is being paid for by the Facility. The work has uncovered the remains of Honey Bee hives, which were temporarily established between the inner and outer walls of the shed during the summers of 2010 and 2011. Unfortunately, all that remained was the wax honeycomb and not the honey.

Dave Wareing (DPW) is due to retire in February 2013. He was a member of the Aberystwyth University team that was involved with the construction of the MST radar. He has spent much of the subsequent time based at the site, albeit working with GV on the lidars and the boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP). He has aided the MST Radar project in numerous ways, for which DAH expressed his appreciation. It is likely that DPW will continue to work part-time. Nevertheless, Facility users will no longer be able to assume that the site is occupied on a full-time basis, e.g. for access and deliveries.

DE reported that he and Nick Hopkins, a Met Office colleague, had visited the MST radar site in December 2012. They were taking advantage of being in mid-Wales whilst making an official visit to Aberporth. Nick Hopkins is the co-ordinator for safeguarding the Met Office's radar operations, e.g. dealing with wind farm applications.

The EUCOS E-WINPROF programme is about to end, but its activities will be absorbed into the broader E-Profile programme. This will also cover ceilometer observations. Although the Met Office will still provide the data hub, the responsibility for monitoring and support activities will soon be taken over by Météo Suisse. The Met Office will continue to distribute their own monthly model-comparison statistics for the UK-based wind-profilers.

3d) The future of NERC's Services and Facilities

Until now NERC has overseen the operations of its various Services and Facilities (S&F) from a single, central team. However, it is in the process of devolving these responsibilities to the relevant research centres. The atmospheric radar facilities - i.e. the MST Radar Facility, the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), and EISCAT Support - will come under the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS). Funding cuts are expected across S&F as a whole, although exact figures and timings remain to be established.

GV pointed out that NCAS funding, e.g. for the FGAM instruments, is renewed on a yearly basis - not on the five-yearly basis currently used by S&F. DE asked whether this meant that the contract for the supply of wind-profile data to the Met Office would also only be renewable on a yearly basis. GV acknowledged that the inability to plan into the medium term was an issue that needed to be raised within NCAS.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

The tipping bucket rain gauge did not detect the rain events seen by the Vaisala WXT510 between 26th and 29th June 2012. LD found that the inlet was blocked with grass seeds when he cleaned it on the 29th. Although the rain gauge detected events between 18th and 21st August 2012 and between 1st

and 4th September 2012, their durations were considerably longer than those seen by WXT510. Partial blockages of the inlet (first by seeds and then by dead insects) appear to have been responsible in both cases. LD cleaned the instrument on 23rd August and 4th September 2012.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

At the time of the 49th meeting, it had not been possible to establish a dial-up connection with the Frongoch data logger since 25th May 2012. The problem was associated with the telephone line rather than the sensors or the data logger. It was not fixed until 2nd July 2012 that a data connection could be re-established. As a consequence, no surface wind data are available for the period between 25th May and 29th June 2012.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

The precipitation sensor failed to detect 4 rain events that were seen by the tipping bucket rain gauge: on 26th June, 8th July, and 31st August 2012, and on 2nd January 2013. It appears that, in all cases, the rain was falling too gently to generate a detectable piezo-electric signal. It was not necessary to take intervention in any of these cases.

There is a gap in the available data on 10th and 11th September 2012. This was the result of an overnight test of the new MST radar control PC *julius* - see section 4g. The interface between the WXT510 and the existing PC, *augustus*, was through a D-type COM port. These are no longer found on modern PCs. Consequently, an important outcome of the test was that *julius* was still able to acquire the data when using a USB adaptor. Although data were recorded during the test period, it will be necessary to combine the files from both PCs before they can be extracted. DK commented that the Met Office are moving over to using rack-mounted PCs. They make use of special PCI cards for legacy serial connections.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There are a few short gaps in the data acquired between 14:50 and 15:30 UT on 18th October 2012. This was the result of the data acquisition PC *julius* being rebooted.

4e) Sky-camera

There have been no issues with this instrument over the past 6 months.

4f) NLC-camera

It was mentioned at the previous meeting that a trial Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) camera had been installed at the Chilbolton Observatory on 7th June 2012. Despite the predominance of obscured (tropospheric) sky conditions and the and the relatively southerly location of the camera (51.1°N), clear NLCs were observed on the night of 24th/25th June 2012. DAH would like to make the images available in near-real-time for the 2013 NLC season. Amateur observers (in the southern British Isles) could use these to decide whether or not it was worth going out spotting.

4g) MST Radar

DE began this section by presenting monthly model-comparison statistics for the past 6 months. Until October 2012, the EUCOS statistics were generated from comparisons made against the German COSMO model. They are now made using the ECMWF model. This led to noticeable changes in the radiosonde statistics, which is what alerted the Met Office to the switch. The MST radar statistics were less-affected. The Met Office statistics are made against their 1.5 km grid UKV model.

The data quality for the Aberystwyth radar was generally good over the past 6 months. However, the root mean square (RMS) wind component differences were elevated for June 2012. This appears to have been the result of no more than 3 bad data points at altitudes of around 10 km for the period 18:00 - 18:30 UT on 1st June 2012. DK commented that he found the single number EUCOS statistics (which cover all times and all altitudes) rather limiting. He would prefer to see statistics broken down according

to weather patterns. He suspects that under certain conditions the wind-profilers are more accurate than the models.

The performance of the South Uist radar has declined during 2012. The Met Office are considering what they can do about it. DK added that they were planning to upgrade the software and, based on the impact of the Aberystwyth renovation, possibly the hardware. The BLWPs are also due for a mid-life upgrade.

DE has examined two years' worth of monitoring statistics for the Aberystwyth radar. There has consistently been a slight positive speed bias for the radar measurements at the higher levels and a slight negative one below. However, the magnitude of these biases is quite small. GV pointed out that this was to be expected owing to the effects of aspect sensitivity. There is no systematic directional bias.

JP asked which organisations operationally assimilated the radar data.

ACTION ITEM 50.4.1 DE to send DAH a list of the organisations that operationally assimilate the Aberystwyth MST Radar data.

NEW

DAH presented the remainder of this section.

The most significant problem encountered by the radar over the past 6 months was caused by the transmitter that powers antenna sector A repeatedly auto-shutting-down. For reasons that are still not understood, this led to a raised noise level and so to a noticeable reduction in useful altitude cover. The loss of a single transmitter should otherwise be barely detectable. The problem showed up particularly clearly in the m-mode plots, which were routinely used to monitor for it.

Although the problem had been occurring sporadically since the renovation of radar, in March 2011, it became irritatingly-frequent during the summer of 2012. It occurred on 29th June, on 3rd, 12th, 13th, 19th, 29th and 30th July 2012, on 4th, 6th, 10th, 13th, 16th, 20th, 22nd, 23rd and 25th August 2012, and on 1st, 5th, 9th and 13th September 2012. LD made a large number of unscheduled visits to the site in order to minimise the amount of time affected. Nevertheless, it was sometimes over 24 hours before he was able to be there. Frustratingly, all that was required to restart the transmitter was for an appropriate code to be entered on its keypad. The problem was solved by attacking it in two stages.

Firstly, DAH revisited the legacy *txtstatus* computer program, which allows each transmitter to be interrogated remotely. This had never been used in earnest, since the information it provided did not appear to have any diagnostic value. Nevertheless, the transmitters are capable of providing more information than the program was displaying. Once DAH had modified the software, it became clear that the affected transmitter was shutting down with error code 4. Although it's not entirely clear what this means, it does indicate that the transmitter simply needs to be restarted. By contrast, error code 5 indicates a blown high voltage fuse, which must be replaced before the transmitter can be operated. DAH also discovered that it was possible to remotely restart a transmitter that has shut down with error code 4. He wrote new software for this purpose and carried out a successful test of it on 17th August 2012. It was used operationally for the first time on 21st August 2012. This tool meant that it was no longer necessary for LD to make a one hour round trip just to press a few buttons. Moreover, it greatly reduced the amount of time affected by the problem.

Secondly, LD (with help from DPW) focused on the analogue parameter values returned by the *txtstatus* program. He noticed that the heater voltage for the affected transmitter was very close to its 10 V upper limit. In fact, the voltage was closer to 15 V, but appeared as 10 V owing to the gain setting in the measurement circuitry. LD tweaked the gain setting, on 14th September 2012, so that the apparent

heater voltage was comfortably within its permissible limits. The transmitter has operated faultlessly ever since.

As a separate issue, the transmitter powering antenna sector B occasionally blows its choke/fuse, i.e. with error code 5. Although this requires LD to be on site, so that he can replace the choke, it does not result in the raised noise floor. Moreover, it occurs relatively infrequently: on 22nd June 2102, on 10th and 18th July, on 11th September, on 6th, 16th, 24th, 26th, and 28th October, on 1st November 2012, and on 20th January 2013.

The radar control and data acquisition PC *augustus* had been in continuous operation since February 2007. A replacement PC, *julius*, began operations on 18th October 2012 (*augustus* is being kept as a backup). DAH relied on the expertise of Alan Doo, one of the Chilbolton engineers, to get the software working on the new PC. Although they managed to get the main radar control software to work on their first visit to the site, on 10th September 2012, they could not initially get *txstatus* and associated programs to work. Alan subsequently sorted the problem and *julius* was installed on a follow-up visit to site on 18th October 2012.

The radar was stopped briefly on 26th June 2012 so that LD could replace the phasing unit for quad 28. For over a week, the diagnostic information indicated that the unit was "ready, but low power". Although it appeared to return to normal on the morning of the 26th, LD swapped in a spare unit for good measure. Similarly, the radar was stopped on 20th November 2012 so that LD could replace the phasing unit for quad 30.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - GV and EGN

GV pointed out that, within NCAS, the term "FGAM radar" now refers to the new X-band radar.

Data from the BLWP are now being automatically archived at Manchester. Most of the products files are also available through the BADC, albeit spread across a number of campaign-specific directories. GV commented that he would prefer all the files to be available under a single chronologically-arranged directory. DK added that it was important to know when the location of the BLWP changed since the data are sent to the Met Office.

ACTION ITEM 50.5.1 EGN to liaise with GAP in order to sort out the archiving of BLWP data on the BADC.

NEW

The BLWP software was updated in November 2012. The PCA computer can now carry out coherent integration more-quickly than the hardware board. There are plans to double the clock rate used by the board. PCA has suffered from a few failures since August 2012. However, the problems were solved by simply removing and the reinserting its boards. There are plans to increase the data storage capacity of PCA so that the I&Q products can be kept. The PCT computer has also had a software update. It can now display the time series of I&Q data.

The model-comparison statistics provided by the Met Office show that there is a persistent directional bias of around 5° for BLWP data from Cardington. This is not seen for the data from their own BLWP at Chilbolton. The orientation of the instrument at Cardington has been determined to be 71° using a magnetic compass. EGN additionally tried using a smart-phone app, but found that the values fluctuated in the range $83^\circ - 100^\circ$. She speculated that the preponderance of metal in the area might have been affecting the readings. DE asked whether a better compass would help. GV pointed out that they already had a good one. HC asked whether differential GPS could be used. GV clarified that the Cardington site

was the only one for which the absolute wind direction was important. It seems unlikely that the orientation of the BLWP can be determined to an accuracy of better than 2°-3°. Consequently, a correction of 3° has been added to the hardpar file. CFL commented that it was important for such changes to be recorded somewhere.

It has been found that the level of cover in the high-mode can be increased slightly by changing the signal-to-noise ratio threshold in the processing. However, it has little effect in the low-mode. Updates have been made to the IDL code. It is now possible to read in Degreane files covering a variety of version numbers. Moreover, it is now possible to read in files which cover only a single beam pointing direction. This has finally allowed access to some old data, which have not previously been accessible.

The BLWP was operated at the MST radar site, in support of the DIAMET campaign, between August 2011 and February 2012. Since then it has been at Cardington. It will be redeployed to Davidstow, in Cornwall, for the CONvective Precipitation Experiment (COPE) between June and August 2013. A variety of other instruments - including the new FGAM mobile X-band radar, the FAAM aircraft, and the Met Office's weather radar network - will also be contributing. There are problems with broadband access and electricity supply at the site. DK pointed out that the Met Office have made use of 3G modems where no wired connection was available. DE pointed out that BLWP data would be available from the Met Office's nearby Camborne and Dunkeswell sites. EGN commented that she was unsure whether the dual polarisation capability would be ready on the Met Office's weather radars in time.

5b) University of Manchester instruments - GV

A new laser has been installed for the water vapour lidar system. It was no longer possible to get flash lamps for the old one. The new laser operates at 30 Hz (compared to 10 Hz) and has 50% more power at 355 nm. The counting unit will be updated, reducing vertical resolution in favour of increasing reliability. The ozone system, which is currently giving trouble, will be improved in the future.

HMAR reported that the Elight lidar was in good working condition. It had remained functional for the entirety of the CLEARFLO campaign during the summer of 2012 - see section 6b. There are no immediate plans for it for 2013. The Leosphere lidar has been returned from the manufacturer, although it is still not working. It will support COPE if it is possible to get it functioning by the summer.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

DAH read out a report from Jon Jones (JJ), who was not at the meeting. There was no news specifically about the GPS receiver based at the MST radar site.

The Met Office are in the process of buying 10 new Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receivers. Ideally these will be deployed to new locations. However, if resources do not allow this, they will be used to replace older units. The COST Action (ES1206) proposal that JJ was leading has been successful. The action will start in the the next few months and will run for 4 years. More details can be found at http://www.cost.eu/domains_actions/essem/Actions/ES1206.

JJ has set up a new real-time GPS processing system. This increases the availability of files - within the Met Office's operational meteorological database (MetDB) and the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) Global Telecommunications System (GTS) - from once every hour to once every 15 minutes. The new files can now be used for assimilation trials etc.

A new system has also been set up to process a global network of sensors. The aim for 2013 is to greatly increase the number of sites used, particularly in data sparse regions of the world e.g. in Australia and South Africa.

An updated version (v5.2) of the Bernese processing software is available and will be implemented in

2013. The main development is that it is multi-GNSS capable, i.e. it has access to more satellites than are available within the American GPS system. Moreover, it incorporates advanced mapping functions based on ECMWF data. Previously, it was only possible to assume a horizontally-stratified atmosphere.

5d) Lightning detector - DAH

This instrument continues to operate without the need for any attention.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) MST Radar and FGAM profiler winds compared to Capel Dewi radiosondes - CFL

CFL's motivation for carrying out this analysis was that he could not find any independent estimates of the accuracy of winds measured by Degreane BLWPs (Degreane estimate it to be within 10%). Using 150 m sampling interval data from the FGAM BLWP, he found typical RMS differences (in time) between 30 minute averaged wind speeds of approximately 1.5 m s^{-1} . The values were similar when considering orthogonal wind components and when considering 15 and 5 minute averages. The values were slightly larger for 75 m sampling interval data.

Co-located BLWP and radiosonde data are available from a number of recent field campaigns (conducted by CFL, Dan Housley, and Bogdan Antonescu). This allowed CFL to calculate the RMS differences between the winds measured by the two techniques. As might be expected, the differences were largest in the lowest 200 m above the ground. This is where the winds are most-influenced by local effects and where the BLWP signal processing has to apply special filters. At higher altitudes the differences are typically in the range $1 - 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The analysis was carried out separately for BLWP observations made at vertical intervals of 187, 150, 75 and 35 m. For these cases there were 6, 44, 46, and 10 radiosondes available, respectively.

A similar analysis was used to compare 63 instances of (150 m range resolution) MST radar and radiosonde winds. The RMS differences ranged from approximately 2 m s^{-1} at the lowest altitudes (i.e. around 2 km) to 4 m s^{-1} in the upper troposphere and above. The length of time averaging used for the MST radar data - over 15, 30 or 60 minutes - had little effect. The results were similar for 68 comparisons made with 300 m range resolution MST radar data. It is not clear whether the increase in RMS differences with increasing altitude is a result of the horizontal separation between the measurements being larger or of the wind speeds being larger. In order to test this, CFL looked at the RMS differences between the winds derived from complementary beams. The values (around 0.02 m s^{-1}) were much lower than he had expected. They were also significantly lower, at the higher altitudes, for observations made in 2012 compared to those made in 2009 and 2010. This is attributed to the effects of the renovation in 2011. The RMS differences between complementary beam winds and the variance between adjacent samples in time both increase with increasing wind speed. However, it's not clear whether faster winds are inherently more variable or whether this is a measurement uncertainty. Faster winds lead to wider signals (through beam broadening), which have a larger scope for uncertainty in the radial velocity.

6b) Initial results from CLEARFLO using the Elight lidar at RAL - HMAR

During the summer of 2012, HMAR operated the Elight lidar at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in support of the Clean Air For London (CLEARFLO) campaign. RAL is approximately 90 km to the west of Central London and was chosen as a rural, nominally-upstream site. The Leosphere lidar was operated at Detling in Kent, a nominally-downstream site approximately 60 km to the east of Central London. Nevertheless, HMAR has focused on low-level wind directions of between 70° and 120° , for which the air seen at RAL should have first passed over London - but might be characterised more by its time spent over mainland Europe.

The 355 nm (i.e. aerosol) backscatter data for 10th and 11th August 2012 show clear diurnal cycles in boundary layer (BL) development over RAL. In the early hours of the 11th, there is an elevated region of

strong backscatter, which is apparently above the nocturnal BL. HMAR speculates that this is a region of aerosol-rich air that has travelled overnight uncoupled from the BL. JP suggested that the enhanced backscatter could be the result of aerosols swelling in response to increased nocturnal relative humidity. Preliminary ozone observations (derived from the 266 and 299 nm wavelengths) also show some diurnal changes for these days. These are attributed to photochemical reactions. HMAR thinks he can see signs of the region of aerosol-rich air being entrained into the developing BL on the morning of the 11th.

HMAR pointed out that there have been problems with the observations made at 266 nm. GV suggested that the combination of the 289 and 299 nm observations was better for ozone measurements.

6c) Apparent infrared sky and cloud temperatures as measured from Gosport - HAC

This work was motivated by HAC's PhD study into the relationship between MST radar return signal power and the atmospheric humidity field. She has been experimenting with a hand-held infrared (IR) thermometer, which she has been pointing at the sky from her 15th floor flat in Gosport, Hampshire. Since water - in vapour, liquid, or solid phase - is the primary atmospheric substance radiating within the relevant 8 - 14 μm wavelength range, these measurements should be able to give some information about it.

The approach was to take a (visual rather than electronic) reading from the IR thermometer every 15 minutes. Measurements were also taken from a regular thermometer (i.e. of the local temperature) and from a barometer. In a case study, the amount of cloud cover increased during the course of a night. The IR sky temperature increased sharply at the first arrival of the cloud and then increased more-slowly towards the local temperature by the time that it started to rain. GV suggested that there may be measurements from Met Office sites which could aid such an investigation - for example, the surface energy balance equipment at Cardington. JP added that the amount of broadband downwelling radiation can be used to infer cloud thickness. He also warned that IR measurements can be influenced by the intervening atmosphere if the device is directed at a distant object.

6d) TROSIAD IOP1 - GV

GV presented this work on behalf of Bogdan Antonescu, who was not at the meeting. It focused on the first Intensive Observation Period (IOP1), on 16th September 2011, of the TROSIAD campaign. During the course of the day, an occluded surface front passed over the MST Radar site. Although the expected change in wind direction was seen at a number of surface stations, the pressure continued to decrease and the temperature increased (after a slight cooling as the frontal rain band passed over). Moreover, there was a second rain band, in addition to the expected convective one. An upper-level Potential Vorticity (PV) anomaly is thought to be responsible for these atypical features.

The FAAM aircraft deployed dropsondes along an East-West flight path at 53.5°N, i.e. slightly to the north of the MST Radar site. There was no evidence of a horizontal gradient in potential temperature, which suggests that the front was principally a surface feature. The MST radar observations show the tropopause fold associated with the PV anomaly. They also show evidence of convection. Although, in the literature, such lower and upper level features are often thought to be related, in this case they clearly were not. JP suggested using trajectory analysis to see whether the features evolved separately or together. GV added that the model gave a good representation of the position of the surface trough but significantly underestimated its intensity. However, he was pleased with the data provided by the MST radar and the FGAM BLWP, which was also operated at the radar site.

6e) Volcanic Ash Advisory (VAA) Lidar Net- DK

The Icelandic volcanic ash incidents of 2010 and 2011 caused severe flight disruptions and had a significant economic impact. The airlines complained that there was insufficient justification for the closure of airspace. It was clear that the Met Office's Volcanic Ash Advisory (VAA) service would have to be improved and that a new observing system would be required in order to achieve this. The existing Laser

Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) network does not provide sufficient information.

The minimal requirements for the new instruments have been established through discussions with experts within the lidar community. The plan is to have 10 lidar systems: 9 at fixed sites and one mobile instrument. Each one will operate at two wavelengths (355 and 1064 nm) and have 3 receiving channels - a co-polar channel for each wavelength and a cross-polar channel. One unit will additionally have a 387 nm Raman channel for calibration purposes. The colour ratio will be used to infer particle sizes and the cross-polar information will be used to determine the particle shapes. Each lidar will be complemented by a multi-channel sun photometer, which will include 355 and 1064 nm wavelengths. Sun-tracking scans will be used to determine the aerosol optical depth (AOD) and Almuantar tracking (i.e. parallel to the horizon) will be used to determine the aerosol size distributions. Development of improved methods lies outside of the scope of the project.

The project has progressed to the stage of selecting suitable models and manufacturers. The plan is to initially buy a single lidar, which can be tested extensively before the others are procured. All of the Sun Photometers will be bought together at the early stage. It will be 3 years before all of the lidar sites are ready, but some will become operational after only 18 months. The software for the existing LCBR instruments can be used for the new network although development will be required to handle the Sun Photometers.

7. Any Other Business

The next Experimenters' meeting, to be held at the Cosener's House, was provisionally scheduled for Thursday 20th June 2013.